

Dyes Derived from 5-Hydroxy Perinaphthindan 1,3-Dione

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Several merocyanines and oxonols ($n = 1$ and 2) have been synthesised from 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione and variable basic nuclei. Utilising their absorption maxima data the basicity of different basic nuclei used in the dye condensation has been evaluated.

In our present investigation a number of merocyanines (I, $n = 1$ and 2) have been synthesised from 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1:3 dione by condensing its acetanilido methylene and acetanilido allylidene intermediates with various 2-methyl quaternary salts in the presence of acetic anhydride and triethylamine.

B = Benzothiazole Quinoline-2 etc.

5-Hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione used as the keto methylene compound was prepared by condensing β -naphthyl methyl ether with malonyl chloride in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride according to Rephael Black *et al.*¹.

Acetanilido methylene and acetanilido allylidene intermediates from 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione were prepared by condensing it with diphenyl formamidine and beta anilino acrolein anil hydrochloride respectively in the medium of acetic anhydride according to our previous procedure². The merocyanines ($n = 1$ and 2) were prepared by heating the acetanilido methylene and acetanilido allylidene intermediates with various 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salts in acetic anhydride and triethylamine.

Utilising the absorption maxima data of the dyes the deviations have been calculated according to Brooker³. Since in a series of merocyanines containing the same acidic nucleus and variable basic nuclei, the deviation is maximum for the least basic nucleus, the relative decreasing order of basicity follow the following sequence; which agrees

Quinoline-4 > Quinoline-2 > 4-Phenyl thiazole satisfactorily with our previous findings⁴.

Experimental

2-(Acetanilido methylene) 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione :

A mixture of 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione (0.9 gm) and diphenyl formamidine (1.2 g) were heated under reflux in acetic anhydride for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product which separated on cooling was washed with water and finally crystallised from alcohol. Yield—40%; m.p.—250°. (Found, C, 73.62; H, 4.07, Formula $C_{20}H_{15}NO_4$ requires C, 73.95; H, 4.20%).

2-(3'-Acetanilido allylidene) 5-hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione :

5-Hydroxy perinaphthindan 1,3-dione (1 gm) and beta anilino acrolein anil hydrochloride (1.2 g) were boiled for 10 min in dry acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate (0.5 g). The compound which separated on cooling was washed with water and finally with acetone and was used directly for dye formation. Yield—40%, m.p. 280°.

General procedure for the preparation of merocyanines :

A mixture of perinaphthindane 1,3-dione intermediate (0.01M) and 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salt (0.01M) were heated in acetic anhydride (10 ml) and a drop of triethylamine for 15 min. The solid separated on cooling was crystallised from alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of various merocyanines prepared by the above procedure have been recorded in Table 1.

Bis-(5-Hydroxy perinaphthindane, 1,3-dione (2) methin Oxonol :

Perinaphthindane 1,3-dione (0.42 g) and diphenyl formamidine (0.19 g) were refluxed in acetic anhydride (10 ml) and a drop of triethylamine for 30 min. On cooling the product separated as yellow solid. It was crystallised from ethanol. Yield—55%, m.p. 215°. The dye shows an absorption maxima at 480 nm in ethanol.

Bis-(5-Hydroxy perinaphthindane 1,3-dione (2) trimethin Oxonol :

It was prepared as above from the dione with beta anilino acrolein anil hydrochloride. Yield—30%, m.p. 200°.

The compound shows an absorption at 555 nm in ethanol.

TABLE I—MEROOCYANINES. I

Nature of the nucleus B	Value of 'n'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} m μ	%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	1	60	> 250	500	61.32	61.85	5.63	5.84
-do-	2	40	230	590	64.12	64.35	5.72	5.99
Quinoline-2	1	50	> 260	510	79.03	79.15	4.38	4.48
-do-	2	35	240	600	79.19	80.00	4.51	4.69
Quinoline-4	1	45	> 270	560	79.32	79.15	4.32	4.48
-do-	2	40	> 250	640	80.16	80.00	4.15	4.69

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